

SERVICE MARKETING IN THE HEALTH INSTITUTIONS

Yildirim S.

Dr.

*Azerbaijan State University of Economics,
Department of Business.*

Abstract

Health institutions that constantly develop and implement viable and evidence-based strategies are one step ahead of their competitors. Thorough investigations of failed health institutions reveal that the main reasons for the failure in most of the cases are the wrong and inapplicable strategies. Therefore, rigorous design and careful execution of viable strategies are the key factors for health institutions to sustain their lives.

Determining the service areas of health institutions also depends on implementing successful and applicable strategies. Such strategies enable health institutions to conduct comprehensive analyses of the health needs of the population in order to determine the prospective services and service areas.

In this study, we employ the needs assessment process and use national and international sources to study how the health institutions should determine potential services and service areas. In addition, we provide a detailed analysis of the concept of health needs to set up a background for the discussion of service marketing determination process.

Keywords: Service Marketing, Health Institutions, Health Need, Health Need Process.

INTRODUCTION

The most important responsibility of health institution managers is to improve the health level of the community. For this purpose, managers must determine what services to provide and what area (region, market) they will supply these services. Determining the services and the service area also enables the institution to raise its performance and gain competitive advantage. As a first step, managers should determine the health needs of the population in the primary service area. In the second step, they should decide on the health services that will meet these needs. In fact, people generally want to have access to certain health services and health resources, specifically to these services and resources proven to meet urgent health needs and improve overall health level. Hence, the answer to the question of how to determine health needs becomes crucial. To determine health needs, it is necessary to study the population, its demographic features, physical and social environmental conditions, health status history, and public health policies.

Service area choice is one of the most crucial establishment process decisions for health institutions. Therefore, health institutions must examine the population and population dynamics, health attitudes of the population, per capita income and income distribution, environmental health circumstances, and current and potential rivals. Quantitative and qualitative data, and managerial analyses of these data about the chosen service area will determine the variety and scope of the services to be provided, and the expected demand for the services. MacStravic (1978) defines the service area as a group of people who are likely to have a specific need for a certain service and are likely to use a particular resource combination for that service.

Strategies designed without sufficient knowledge about the service area (market) decrease the competitiveness of the institution and pose a threat to its survival.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to examine how an institution should determine the health needs of the population in its service area. The service area refers to the region where the health institution is located and the population living in that region. Therefore, we study the managerial processes and activities to accurately determine the health needs of the population and plan how to generate sufficient resources to meet these needs. The health needs determination and assessment process also provide significant experience for healthcare institutions' managers in designing institutional vision and strategy. Therefore, try to supplement our discussion of health needs evaluation process with current field examples from the healthcare sector.

METHODOLOGY

In accordance with the purpose of the study, we conduct a detailed and systematic review of the related literature on health needs determination and service area. We provide a general assessment of the main findings of the literature regarding health needs determination methodologies. Quantitative and qualitative data and findings of empirical examples reveal the importance of developing an exhaustive procedure for determining health needs in the service area. Hence, we also try to enrich theoretical discussions with recent empirical examples.

AN OVERVIEW OF SERVICE AND SERVICE AREA ANALYSIS

During the environmental analysis process, managers must closely focus on the service area and the health needs of the population living in that area. That is, as depicted in Figure 1, managers must first determine the services they will provide and the service area to gain a competitive advantage in the sector. As stated above, the service area refers to the region where the health institution is located, as well as the population living in that region. From a marketing perspective, the service area can be seen as the market of the health institution. Therefore, the concepts of service area, service region, and market are used interchangeably. The

analysis of the service area includes the determination of the services to be provided and the examination of health service demand dynamics of the population in the area.

Figure 1. Health Services and the Service Area

THE DETERMINATION OF THE SERVICES TO BE PROVIDED

To determine and plan the health services to be provided, the health needs of the population living in the service area should be analyzed, and a relationship

between the health needs and the services to be provided should be established to meet these needs, (Acheson, 1978; Magi and Allender, 1981). Once the health services to meet the health needs have been determined, the necessary resources to provide these services can be allocated more easily and rationally.

Figure 2. Health Needs and Health Services: Humanistic Approach¹

Service planning not based on the health needs of the community may lead to problems for the health institution arising from excess demand (marked by increasing patient density, long queues, and decreasing service quality) or excess supply (marked by rising unused capacity, declining productivity, and growing

costs). Furthermore, if the health needs of the community are not met adequately and in a timely manner, the health status of the community will deteriorate. The process of developing appropriate strategies for identifying, analyzing, and meeting the health needs of the community is called "health needs assessment" (Weney

¹ Donebadian (cited by Acheson, 1978) proposes a resource-based model to link health needs and health services as depicted in Figure 2. In this model, prospective services are determined based on available resources, and then the services are associated with the needs. More specifically, the resource-based establishes the link between health needs and services taking resources as given. Although this approach may be applicable to private health institutions, it is not relevant to the public sector. It is because, the primary responsibility of the welfare state is to meet all the health needs of society. Therefore, the welfare state must adopt a perspective of generating required resources to meet everyone's health needs in the society. On the other hand, the resource-based approach assumes that health needs are unlimited, while resources are limited. Furthermore, this approach treats health services as ordinary consumer goods.

and Kaluzny, 1998:33-34). Through health needs assessment, health institution managers can develop institutional and operational strategies to determine which (case mix), for whom (service area, population, population groups), how much (service planning), where (hospital, day surgery center), how (treatment plans), and using which resources (strategic human resource planning, bed planning) to provide the services. Before discussing the process of health needs assessment, it is necessary to define and explain the concept of health needs.

HEALTH NEEDS

Health need can be defined in the simplest term as the difference between the “ideal health status” and the “current health status. The World Health Organization defines “ideal health” as “a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being”. If an individual is experiencing complications in her/his physical, mental, or social well-being, it can be inferred that the individual has a health need. That is, the concept of health need can be understood as any deviation from the complete or ideal health status that limits an individual’s potential. Bradshaw (1972) divides health needs into four categories:

i. Perceived Need: This category is pertaining to the individuals’ perception of deviations in their health status. That is, perceived need is based on the individuals’ subjective evaluations. An example of perceived health need is an individual’s having a burning sensation in her/his chest.

ii. Expressed Need: Expressed need is the transformation of perceived need into a demand. An example of an expressed need is an individual’s going to a health institution when she/he is having a burning sensation in her/his chest.

iii. Normative Need: Normative need arises when a physician diagnoses a deviation in an individual’s health status. The normative need may be completely different from the perceived or expressed need. For example, a patient who feels chest pain (perceived

need) and goes to the hospital (expressed need) may receive a diagnosis of a stomach ulcer. Then, the treatment put forward to cure the stomach ulcer refers to normative need. However, it is not necessary for the need to be perceived or expressed for the normative need to arise. Sometimes individuals may not even be aware of deviations in their health statuses. On the other hand, the normative need is closely related to the knowledge and skills of the physicians and the technological capabilities of the health institution.

iv. Comparative Need: The comparative need is based on comparisons of health levels between individuals or regions. If the vaccination rate for infants in region A is 100%, but in region B it is 70%, then it can be inferred that region B requires vaccination services.

THE EVALUATION OF HEALTH NEEDS

The evaluation of health needs in a health institution is a managerial process composed of gathering and analysis of information to determine the services to be provided. The basic mission of managers in health institutions is to improve the health level of the community they serve. To improve the health level of the community, it is essential to identify the risk factors that may affect the community’s health, measure the community’s health needs, and provide services that meet these needs. The evaluation of health needs provides health institution managers with:

- i. Knowledge about the disease pattern of the population in the service area,
- ii. Guidance on the health needs and priorities of the population or patients who apply for services,
- iii. Identification of unmet health needs in the region or population,
- iv. Rational determination of resources to be used in the production of services to meet needs, and
- v. Help for understanding and prevention of inequalities in the use of health services (Wright, et al., 1998; Weigl et al., 2012).

There is a definite process that must be followed in health needs evolution. We provide the stages of the needs assessment in Figure 3 below.

Şekil 3. Gereksinim Değerlendirme Süreci

Source: Adapted from Petersen and Alexander (2002:25-37).

Planning

The first stage of the health needs assessment process is the planning activities. The planning stage consists of two basic steps. The first step includes preliminary preparations. The following activities are carried out within the scope of the preliminary preparations (Petersen and Alexander, 2002: 26-28):

i. Establishment of the Health Needs Assessment Team and Organization: The health needs assessment team includes public health experts, epidemiologists, statisticians, and health managers. If specific

health needs are to be assessed for a particular health problem (such as cardiology), specialized physicians in the field may also be included in the team.

ii. Determination of the Usage Areas of the Evaluation Studies: Within the scope of the preliminary preparations, the expected benefits of the health needs assessment study and the areas in which it will be used (such as determination of needs levels, service planning, and financing health services) are made clear.

iii. Determination of Stakeholders of Health Needs: It is important to identify stakeholders who may

be directly or indirectly affected by health needs assessments and to ensure their contributions to the assessment process (such as professional organizations and medical specialty associations).

iv. Determination of the Target Population:

One of the critical steps in the health needs assessment process is the determination of the target population. The target population consists of the segments of the population who have current health needs or risk of health needs. For instance, the target population for school health services can be easily determined as “primary and secondary school students”. Similarly, the target population for environmental health services can be determined as the entire population of a country, or a particular city. The target population can be classified as the “population-at-risk”. More specifically, population-at-risk refers to the group of individuals susceptible to a particular disease. For example, the target populations for cervical cancer and prostate cancer are female and male populations, respectively. On the other hand, the target population for occupational diseases is working individuals prone to such diseases (Bonita et al., 2006: 17).

Data Collection

The second stage of the needs assessment process involves data collection activities. Before starting data collection activities, health need indicators must be determined. Health need indicators are criteria that reveal the health level of the population and provide guidance for activities to improve the population’s health level. Examples of these indicators include life expectancy at birth, disease and mortality rates by cause, age, and gender.

Since the 2000s, the health level of countries has been defined by comprehensive measures such as Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY) and Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALY) that quantify the total burden of diseases in the country. DALY is a measure of burden of disease expressed as the number of years lost due to ill-health. A decrease in the DALY value indicates a decline in the burden of disease, that is, a rise in the health level of the population. DALY consists of two main components: (i) Years of Life Lost (YLL) and (ii)

Years Lived with Disability (YLD). YLL refers to lost years of life lost due to premature deaths from diseases. For example, if the average life expectancy in a country is 82 years and a person dies at the age of 70 due to ischemic heart disease, then YLL is 12 years.

A person may become disabled because of a traffic accident. A 10 year life span for a healthy person and a disabled person implies different life qualities. That is, living 10 years in good health and living 10 years with a disability are not considered equal. Therefore, based on health statuses of individuals, different weights ranging from 0 to 1 are assigned to life spans. each disability situation. 0 indicates a state of full health, while means death.

The total DALY value of a country, region, or population is calculated as follows:

$$\text{DALY} = \text{YLL} + \text{YLD}$$

Diseases with high DALY values indicate the diseases that have the greatest impact on the overall health of the population and therefore require intervention.

After health indicators are determined, the data on these indicators are collected, classified, and prepared for analysis. Data can be collected by conducting field research (such as verbal autopsy and household health surveys), from published reports (such as disease burden reports, national health databases², and disease and mortality statistics), or relying on expert opinions (such as Delphi and Nominal Group Techniques) (Veney and Kaluzny, 19).

Analysis

In the analysis stage, the data is analyzed to calculate the indicators (such as DALY) measuring the community’ health level. Another important endeavor undertaken as a part of data analysis is setting priorities. Setting priorities involves ranking health needs according to their degree of importance. For example, if the DALY method is used, the diseases or risk factors with the highest DALY value (such as perinatal causes and ischemic heart diseases) will be at the top of the priority list. We provide a comparison of Years of Life Lost (YLL) values in 2002 and 2019 according to the top 10 causes for Turkey in Table 1.

Table 1.

A Comparison of Years of Life Lost (YLL) Values in 2002 and 2019 According to the Top 10 Causes

Rank	Cause	2002	2019	Change (%)
1	Ischemic Heart Disease	1.770.301	1.788.335	1,02
2	Stroke	474.638	825.066	73,83
3	Trachea, Bronchus, and Lung Cancers	325.095	736.936	126,68
4	Neonatal Diseases	1.974.350	616.006	-68,80
5	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease	311.174	478.505	53,77
6	Congenital Birth Anomalies	984.531	440.984	-55,21
7	Diabetes	313.821	372.907	18,83
8	Chronic Kidney Disease	278.198	357.131	28,37
9	Traffic Accidents	327.791	352.078	7,41
10	Lower Respiratory Tract Infection	752.228	303.432	-59,66

² For the definitions of Health Ministry Türkiye Data Sets, see <http://www.e-saglik.gov.tr/dosyalar/usvs2.pdf>

Source: Ministry of Health (2020). Health Statistics Yearbook, Ünüvar et al., (Ed) (2004). Türkiye Hastalık Yüklü Çalışması,

After prioritizing the population’s health needs, the health services devised meet these needs must be determined. The types and quantities of health services should be determined by a board consisting of medical specialists with profound expertise on the disease. We provide the types and quantities of services for the diagnosis and treatment of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) as an example in Figure 4 (Ministry of Health, 2020).

Figure 4 shows that, if 1,000 patients with a diagnosis of COPD apply to the hospital in a year, 2,000 spirometry tests, 3,000 chest X-rays, and 100 ultrasound services will need to be provided. 28% of patients diagnosed with COPD are hospitalized for an average of 10 days. Therefore, 280 patients will be hospitalized in a year, and 2,800 patient-days of service will be provided to these patients.

Figure 4. Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Diagnostic and Treatment Services

Strategy Development

The assessment of health needs contributes significantly to strategy development efforts in health institutions (Scurlock et al., 2011). In this context, disease burden (DALYs) can be used to analyze the target population (service area or market) and determine the potential number of patients. DALY values calculated by geographic areas (such as region and province), specific age groups (such as 65+ elderly population and reproductive age women), and specific population groups

(such as school-age population and mining sector employees) can help managers to specify the service area. For instance, a hospital following a growth strategy in cardiovascular surgery field can benefit from the disease burden figures for heart disease when deciding in which region to open a neighborhood polyclinic or hospital. Table 2 summarizes the potential strategies a hospital can follow when considering only the disease burden.

Tablo 2.

Hastalık Yüklü ve İzlenebilecek Stratejiler

REGION/MARKET	DISEASE BURDEN	STRATEGIES
A	High	Open a hospital in the region
B	Middle	Open a district/neighborhood polyclinic in the region
C	Low	Promote hospital

In addition to the growth strategies mentioned above, determining the services to be offered also facilitates the decision on strategies with operational dimension. Operational strategies will be formed according to the answers to the following questions:

- Where will the services be provided (hospital, rehabilitation center, day surgery center, or home care)?

- How will the services be provided (stages of the treatment process, clinical guidelines, and pathways)?

- Who will benefit from the services (the entire country, population living in a specific region, private patients, patients covered by the Social Security Institution)?

Resource Allocation

The final stage of the needs assessment process involves planning and allocating the necessary resources to ensure that sufficient services are provided to meet health needs. Resource allocation that is not based on service production plans (such as workforce planning, material planning, and bed planning) can lead to waste of resources and inefficiency problems. We try to explain the relationship between the service provision and resources in a simplified way using the data in Figure 4.

For 1,000 patients with a COPD diagnosis applying to the hospital in a year, 3,000 chest X-rays will be performed, and 2,800 patient days of service will be provided. Assume that a shooting a graph takes 6 minutes, and nursing services provided to a patient admitted to the chest diseases clinic with a COPD diagnosis last for 0.5 hours. Then, the required workload for performing 3,000 chest X-rays is 300 hours ($3000 \times 6 = 8,000$ minutes, 300 hours). The required workload for nursing services is 1,400 hours (for 2,800 patient days).

The Healthcare Implementation Communiqué (SUT) establishes a relationship between the resources and services. Furthermore, SUT sets certain criteria regarding which material or drug will be used and how much for each service.

CONCLUSION

Strategies prepared without sufficient information about the service area may lead to challenges for the health institutions through increasing patient density, causing longer queues, decreasing service quality, increasing idle capacity, reducing efficiency, and increasing costs.

Once health institutions determine their service areas, they should ensure efficient use of resources and a certain standard of service quality in meeting the demand for their services in the service areas. However, they should also provide their services in a timely manner.

Healthcare institution managers can develop evidence-based, feasible, and institutionally appropriate strategies in conjunction with determining health needs. Assessing health needs can provide healthcare

institution managers with information on the population's disease pattern, patients' priorities, unmet health needs, the combination of resources used and services provided, and inequalities that arise during service utilization.

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